

Occupational Stress and Professional Burnout: Public Elementary School Teachers in Focus

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Abstract. The teaching profession has long been argued as one of the most stressful professions to date. This phenomenological inquiry aimed to investigate the experiences of public elementary school teachers in the Department of Education with occupational stress and professional burnout. Following purposive sampling, ten classroom teachers participated in key informant interviews. The findings revealed themes on experiences such as the lack of resources, lack of appreciation, heavy workload and high-pressure expectations. To counter these challenges, the teachers have found the following coping strategies: planning of tasks, collaboration, and approaches in handling learners. Considering the challenges at hand, three educational management insights were generated: overwhelming workload, continued professional development, and strengthened social support. This study provided a benchmark for directions to policymakers and education leaders that in order to effectively address the stress and burnout associated with teachers. Moreover, implications for reflective teaching and administrative practice are noted. The study suggested replication of the issue focusing with other methods, participants, and situations.

KEY WORDS

1. administrative tasks 2. stress 3. burnout

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1. Introduction

Stress among teachers is a prominent and pervasive issue in the education sector. In a broader perspective, this problem poses significant implications for their students and even the whole community. These past few years, there have been several studies that discussed the factors which contribute to teacher stress often leading to professional burnout and job dissatisfaction. In the United Kingdom, it was discovered that factors such as job pressure, management structure of the school, and lack of promotion and status were among of the contributors to teacher stress and dissatisfaction. In fact, teachers were found reporting these stress-related manifestation far higher than other occupational groups (Maelan et al., 2018). Moreover, the problem has extended to other mental health concerns among educators. Mental ill-health due to occupational stress and personal factors were predicted to contribute to teachers' leaving the profession in the UK. Additionally, the ambiguity of educators' role in schools has also placed a great influence on teacher retention. A study conducted by Lizana and Lera (2022) proposed that there is a strong background which indicates that the teaching pro-

profession is one of the most stressful and teachers' mental health has deteriorated further amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of the study suggest that there have been high rates of depression, stress, and anxiety symptoms observed among educators. More so, teachers who are affected by work-family balance were more prone to symptoms of stress and anxiety. Moreover, depression symptoms were higher among women. These are in alignment with the findings of the study of Borg and Riding (1991) which explored the impact of stress on teachers. The results showed that educators who report greater stress were less satisfied with teaching, had more frequency of absences, were more likely to resign and less likely to take up teaching as a career again. This contributes to the risk of educators leaving the profession altogether. In fact, in June 2023, there had been a record high of 40,000 teachers, 9% of the teaching workforce, in England who left the teaching profession (The Guardian, 2023). Numerous factors contribute to the stress experienced by teachers. High workload, heavy administrative responsibilities, lack of control over classroom environments, insufficient resources, and unrealistic expectations are consistently identified as primary sources of stress. Additionally, factors such as classroom discipline issues, time constraints, assessment pressures, and the demand for professional development further compound the stress experienced by educators (Fisher, 2011). In the Philippines, teachers face numerous reasons to be stressed and burnt out. A study conducted by Mingoa (2017) revealed that the five most common reasons why teachers felt stressed were: too much paperwork, high cost of living, insufficient salary, big class sizes, and other affiliations. Moreover, according to Bongco and Ancho (2019), reports claim that teachers' heavy workload leads to high stress level. Groups such as the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) and Teachers' Dignity Coalition (TDC) demanded the Department of Education to assess teachers' workload in order to ensure the physical and mental well-being of teachers. More so, ACT asserted that teachers' workload had only become more burdensome with the implementation of several policies which require much effort. In spite of the presence of several studies that discuss the root causes of stress and burnout among teachers, the problem is still prevalent in the teaching field particularly among public school teachers in the elementary level. This study aimed to shed light on the reasons behind teachers' occupational stress and professional burnout, as well as countercheck if the problems encountered by teachers in the Philippines are similar to that of teachers from other countries. The insights that will be gained from the findings of this study will contribute to the plethora of knowledge in better understanding Filipino teachers' working conditions and what the education sector can do about it.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to provide understanding on the different challenges experienced by teachers in relation to occupational stress and professional burnout, as well as find out the coping strategies they use to counter such problems in the workplace. The study's findings would contribute in the plethora of literature available to better comprehend the scale of teacher stress and burnout in the Philippine education sector.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aims to explore and investigate the experiences with stress and burnout of public-school elementary teachers in the Department of Education.

- (1) What were the experiences of DepEd elementary teachers that led to occupational stress and burnout?
- (2) What were the coping mechanisms used by teachers to counter the problems?

(3) What insights can be drawn from the findings of this study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Occupational Stress Occupational stress refers to the physical and emotional strain resulting from job demands that exceed the worker’s ability to cope effectively. In the teaching profession, it often includes challenges such as workload overload, time pressures, and high expectations from administration, parents, and the community.

Professional Burnout Professional burnout is a state of emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion caused by prolonged stress and frustration within the workplace. In teachers, burnout can manifest as fatigue, lack of motivation, reduced performance, and a sense of detachment from students and colleagues.

Coping Strategies Coping strategies are techniques or methods used to manage and mitigate stress and burnout. In this study, the coping strategies used by teachers include planning tasks, collaborating with peers, and employing specific approaches to effectively manage classroom challenges and interactions with students.

Educational Management Insights Educational management insights are valuable observations derived from research, aimed at improving policy, administrative practices, and teacher support structures within educational institutions. In the context of this study, insights focused on managing teacher workload, promoting professional development, and enhancing social support systems within schools.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The results of the study about DepEd teachers’ stress and burnout will shed light on the current state of teachers’ well-being. Particularly, the following will benefit from the findings: Educators. Understanding the causes and effects of teacher stress and burnout is crucial for safeguarding the mental and emotional health of educators, ensuring their overall well-being, job satisfaction, and retention within the profession. Students. Teacher burnout directly impacts student learning outcomes. By addressing and mitigating educator stress, it’s possible to create a more conducive learning environment, enhancing students’ academic achievements and socio-emotional development. School Com-

munity. High rates of teacher turnover due to burnout incur substantial costs for schools and districts. Investigating stress factors can help in implementing support mechanisms that promote teacher longevity and stability within the education system. Administrators. Studying stress and burnout provides insights for administrators into the need for ongoing professional development and support structures tailored to teachers’ evolving needs, fostering a more resilient and adaptable workforce. Department of Education. Research on teacher burnout informs the development of policies at institutional and governmental levels, aiding in the creation of supportive environments, workload management, and mental health resources for educators.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is grounded on Job Demand-Control (Support) Theory and Effort-Reward Imbalance Model (ERI model) developed by Johannes. In order to understand better the dynamics of the factors and reasons which contribute to teacher stress

and burnout, the aforementioned theories will be used in the research process. For more than two decades, the Job Demand-Control (JCD) model and its enlarged variant, the Job Demand-Control-Support model, have dominated the study of occupational stress. According to the

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

JCD model, the interaction between two aspects of the work environment—psychological job demands and job control—causes job strain. Workload has historically been associated with psychological pressures, which primarily operated in terms of time pressure and role conflict (Karasek, 1985). However, the contemporary definition of psychological demand is now defined by interpersonal conflict aspects, cognitive and emotional demands. Job control, also known as decision latitude in the literature, is the ability of an individual to direct their work-related activities. It is characterized by two essential elements: (a) decision authority (the employee’s capacity to make decisions about their jobs); and (b) skill discretion (the range of skills the employee uses on the job). According to the JCD theory, people who have high expectations and limited control are more likely to feel psychological pressure at work, endure work-related stress, and eventually have poor physical and mental health. Social support was eventually added to the model as a social dimension. According to the JCDS model, social support can reduce the harmful effects of workplace

stress on a worker’s physical and mental health. According to this model, employees who experience iso-strain—a condition marked by high demands and inadequate control—along with low workplace support are most at risk for having poor physical and mental health (Towler, 2020). Meanwhile, Johannes created the Effort-Reward Imbalance model in the early 1990s. According to this idea, effort put forth at work is linked with benefits in the form of money, respect, and career possibilities as part of a psychological contract based on the social reciprocity norm (Ren et al., 2019). An imbalance (non-reciprocal) between the effort put forth and the benefits gained can lead to a stress reaction, which in turn increases the risk of illness. According to Siegrist, there are three situations in which stress relating to the disparity between effort and rewards can materialize: employee has little option with alternative job opportunities; accepts the imbalance out of the expectation that working conditions will be improved in the future; and copes with work demands by means of over commitment.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology used in this study which comprises the philosophical assumption, qualitative assumption, research design, research participants, role of the researcher, data gathering, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and ethical considerations.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions— Whether a researcher is aware of it or not, they always bring certain beliefs and philosophical presuppositions to a study. These assumptions and precepts can occasionally have a significant influence on how one tackles research issues, develops research questions, and gathers data. We develop these opinions and assumptions during our educational training by reading scholarly books and journal articles, getting advice from mentors, and taking part in scholarly societies. The two hurdles in handling them are identifying these attitudes and assumptions and choosing whether to actively integrate them in the study. According to Creswell (2013), one could begin the process by thinking about why it's important to understand and be able to explain the philosophical presuppositions that drive qualitative research. According to Creswell (2014), understanding philosophical presuppositions is essential because it affects how one formulates problems, research questions, and information-seeking tactics. These assumptions are also based on one's training and reinforced by the scholarly community in which they are employed. Additionally, the researcher benefits from knowing the reviewers' positions on key epistemological issues when they make philosophical assumptions about the work. In qualitative research, paradigms are philosophical presuppositions and beliefs. They include ontology, epistemology, axiology, and technique. Axiology examines how values play a role in research, ontology involves views about the nature of reality, epistemology addresses what constitutes knowledge and how knowledge claims are supported, and methodology refers to the research process (Creswell, 2014). According to Creswell, the nature of reality and its attributes are related to the ontological problem of philosophical presumptions and beliefs. When conducting qualitative research, researchers are accepting the concept of various realities. Like the study's participants and readers, various researchers embrace various realities. Qualitative researchers perform studies on individuals with the goal of reporting these various realities. The use of many types of evidence in themes that employ the actual words of various people and portray various viewpoints is one way to demonstrate the existence of numerous realities. In qualitative research, the epistemological premise dictates that researchers attempt to establish a personal connection with the participants. According to individual viewpoints, the subjective evidence is put together, and this is how knowledge is discovered, according to Creswell. The field in which the participants live and work becomes crucial for conducting studies since these circumstances are crucial for comprehending what the participants are saying. This is done in an effort to reduce the distance and subjectivity between the researcher and the subjects of the study (Guba and Lincoln, 1988; referenced in Creswell, 2014). Finally, the axiological presumption relates to the values that the researcher brings to the study, and in qualitative research, the researcher makes their values explicit in the study, according to Creswell. In a qualitative study, the researchers actively disclose their personal beliefs and prejudices as well as the value-laden character of the data they collected on the ground. They also acknowledge the value-laden nature of the research.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Individuals desire to understand their reality and come up with their unique meanings which correlate to their personal experiences using social constructivism as a framework for qualitative assumptions. However, these meanings are not innate in every person. They are multiple and varied, which leads the researcher to investigate the complexity of views instead of narrow down

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—The study used a qualitative-inquiry-based phenomenological research design with open-ended questions. This type of research design focuses on the researcher identifying the essence of the descriptions of the participants about a phenomenon. The process follows the researcher setting aside his or her personal experiences in order to arrive at an understanding of the experiences of the study participants. Through this, the researcher was able to create a description of the teachers' shared meanings in connection to their experiences with occupational stress and professional burnout. Phenomenological studies are effective in highlighting participants' individual perceptions and experiences; thus, challenging

2.4. *Research Participants*—The study will be conducted in DepEd Region XI – Davao City Division. There will be 10 participants from an elementary school in Davao City who will be key informants and they would be purposely selected on the basis of the nature of their work as classroom teachers in the elementary level. The purposeful selection of an informant based on the informant's personal characteristics is known as the judgment sampling or purposive sampling technique. It is a non-random technique that does not require underlying ideas or a predetermined number of informants (Bernard, 2006). The researcher determined what information was necessary to have and then set out to locate those who could

the meanings into few ideas or categories. Moreover, researchers have a purpose to heavily rely on the participants' perspectives. These subjective meanings, most often than not, are scrutinized in historical and social contexts. This means that they are developed using interactions with other people as well as cultural and historical conventions which work in people's lives instead of merely being imprinted on them.

normal and structural assumptions. Moreover, including an interpretive factor permits the research to inform, question or support actions and policies by using as a foundation for practical theory (Lester, 1999). As an outcome, the research method becomes a good fit for apprehending the experiences of educators. Moreover, real life situations have to be explored in terms of their contextual nature as perceived by the participants. As such, phenomenology is an applicable and suitable technique to explore the topics about the experiences of teachers exposed to occupational stress and professional burnout. Common themes that will come up will be analyzed, coded, and interpreted from all the interviews.

and would be willing to share it due to their training or expertise. Through the key informant technique, where one or a small number of people are asked to serve as guides to the phenomenon, deliberate sampling is demonstrated. Key informants are perceptive, self-aware participants in the community of interest who are knowledgeable about the subject and are able and eager to contribute their insights. Specifically, the inclusion criteria cover the following: (1) permanent DepEd teachers serving in the Division of Davao City, (2) teachers who are handling elementary learners. Moreover, the following exclusion criteria were included: (1) non-teaching staff; (2) permanent teachers who are handling secondary school students.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Since qualitative researches are in-depth in nature, ethical questions are particularly relevant. Conducting an in-person interview with a set of participants may raise ethical concerns that are serious. Thus, consent must be given freely and the study participants should comprehend what is being asked from them. More so, they have to be competent to provide consent before it is given. With that being said, the study participants need to be provided with all the information that they need in order to arrive at an educated choice of whether or not they will continue to take part in the study. Moreover, they have to be given the chance to exercise their freedom to refuse participation should they choose to do so. Ac-

ording to Kaiser (2009), this suggests that by not releasing the identities of the participants or identifying any key information during the data collection, analysis, and interpretation process, the researcher has ensured that their privacy has been safeguarded. All the more, the researcher has undertaken the required precautions to deliver the study in relation to the ethical guidelines for conducting qualitative researches. The researcher ensured that the study participants knew all the things that there is to know about the study and they grasped the ideas presented to them. Additionally, the ethics committee of the graduate school of Rizal Memorial Colleges, composed of authorities in-charge of verifying and approving the process has required the researcher to present necessary documentation.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—In qualitative research, the researcher's job is to obtain the necessary data while examining the opinions and feelings of the study subjects regarding the topic under investigation. To put it mildly, this is not an easy process. This means getting people to talk on subjects that could be extremely

sensitive to them. Reliving past experiences can be difficult at times, especially if they were unpleasant and are still fresh in the participant's mind. As a researcher, my first responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data, regardless of the method used to collect it. Participants must be provided with clear and concise protective methods.

2.7. *Data Collection*—In gathering data, the researcher prepared the interview guide which comprises three main significant questions, inquiring about the experiences of public-school teachers with occupational stress and professional burnout. Deliberation has been made on the part of identifying the problems of educators in the effort to determine the root causes of the aforementioned difficulties. Afterwards, the interview guide had been evaluated by experts. Furthermore, ethical protocols had been observed and applied in the implementation of the collected data. A letter has been sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, Division Office of the DepEd, District Supervi-

sor, and to the Principal of the Schools to ask for permission to conduct the study. After the letter has been approved, the conditions that were set by the approving authority has been considered and met. The interview sessions followed after that. The sessions were conducted in public places with private areas in order to safeguard the confidentiality of the participants. The interviews were likewise audio recorded with the participants' consent. Additionally, participants were instructed not to refer to individuals or locations by their names during the interview. I explained the study's goals, the interview's format, and the nature, advantages, and dangers of involvement to each participant throughout the

interview. They were also told that participation was optional and that rigorous confidentiality rules would apply to all information gathered. They were made aware that while their participation would not result in financial gain, it might help spread knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation. Following, the note taker and recorder were used to transcribe the In-depth Interviews (IDI) processes. In order to confirm the informants' responses were genuine, I also used the trial version of the Inscribe software to record their responses. Through this technique, I was able to connect with the interview subjects and elicit open and honest responses. After the

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Before assessing the quality of the collected data, there are several steps that have been undertaken in this qualitative research design. The methodologies used in this study have access to the mentioned basic tasks. First, the researcher created plans to ensure the safety of both the data and original materials used in the process of data collection (Capella University, n.d.). More so, the identification and privacy of the participants have been safeguarded. The raw data was then converted and transcribed following the appropriate format, and in order to confirm assure more safety measures a master copy as well as other backup copies have likewise been created should mis-

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The conceptual framework for this phenomenological inquiry illustrates the process of understanding participants' lived experiences of occupational stress and professional burnout. The research begins with in-depth interviews, which serve as the primary data collection method. These interviews allow participants to share their personal experiences in detail. Following the interviews, the data is organized, listened to, and

IDI procedure, I restated or distilled the data before presenting it to them to attest to its accuracy. Participants are given the opportunity to critically evaluate and comment on findings by sharing them with them. The summaries that were offered to the participants received unanimous approval from them as an authentic depiction of their ideas, sentiments, and experiences. Their assurance of the information's accuracy and comprehensiveness in this study significantly increased the study's credibility. Accordingly, the information acquired from the IDI was arranged into themes for study.

takes are made. Finally, thematic analysis has been used for the analysis of the patterns that occurred. In the examination of interview data, themes are sought to be found in patterns. One benefit of thematic analysis is that it is a flexible method that can be used for both more deductive studies where the researcher knows exactly what he or she is interested in as well as for exploratory studies where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for. No matter what kind of study is being conducted or for what reason, the most crucial aspect of the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and makes an effort to accurately describe the interview's findings (Mertens, 2020).

transcribed, ensuring that all narratives are accurately captured. The next step involves developing significant statements from the transcribed data, which are then grouped into themes that highlight common patterns and insights.

Once themes are identified, the researcher provides a textural description of the participants' experiences, detailing what the participants went through in their own words. In parallel, a structural description is developed to

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

explain how these experiences unfolded and the context in which they occurred. Finally, these descriptions are combined to form a compound understanding of the phenomenon, reinforced by participants' verbatim narratives and rele-

vant literature. This comprehensive description sheds light on the essence of the participants' experiences and provides a deeper understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—A study's validity is important because it demonstrates how widely the research methodology was used and accepted by the general public as well as the relevant academic, professional, and policy communities (Nowell et al., 2017). Establishing credibility is one way that researchers can persuade themselves and their readers that their study findings are important. In order to further develop the idea of trustworthiness, Lin-

coln and Guba established the four criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability in 1985. Credibility. The credibility of a study is established, according to Lincoln and Guba (1985, quoted in Nowell et al., 2017), when the primary researchers or readers are placed in a situation where they can relate to the experience being examined. According to Tobin Begley (2004), cited in Nowell et al. (2017), this criterion focuses on differ-

ences between respondents' perspectives and researchers' interpretations of those perspectives. These academics suggested a range of strategies for determining credibility, such as sustained attention-promoting activities, persistent observation, triangulation in data collection, and triangulation among researchers. A debriefing was also recommended as a means of obtaining outside validation of the research technique. Transferability. The applicability of findings to different contexts is the focus of this criterion. Transferability in qualitative designs is frequently assessed on a case-by-case basis because researchers frequently are unsure of which sites may want to implement their findings. However, in order for interested parties to decide whether or not the findings apply to their specific environment, researchers must still pro-

vide thorough descriptions (Nowell et al., 2017). Dependability. If the researchers can guarantee that the procedure that they are utilizing to conduct the study is logical, traceable, and properly recorded, this requirement can be satisfied. One technique for assessing a process' reliability is auditing it (Koch, 1994, referenced in Nowell et al., 2017). Confirmability. This criterion aims to prove that the research's interpretations and conclusions may be inferred directly from the data. To meet this criterion, the researcher must provide examples of how results and interpretations were arrived at. Additionally, when the appropriate degrees of dependability, credibility, and transferability are attained, this criterion can be achieved (Lincoln and Guba, 1985 quoted in Nowell et al., 2017).

3. Results and Discussion

This section of the study shows the findings to the research questions according to the responses of the participants. The respondents presented their experiences on the challenges with occupational stress and burnout along with their coping strategies and the insights they gained out of those experiences. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the response of the participants. The findings of the thematic analysis based on the themes and subthemes identified are presented in this chapter.

3.1. *DepEd teachers' experiences leading to burnout* —

3.1.1. *Lack of Resources*—Teachers' lack of access to learning materials is one of the themes evident in the participants' response. In order for the teaching and learning process to properly take place, teachers and students should have access to resources that will help them make the most out of the learning experience. A study conducted by Kaufhold et al. (2006) suggests that the lack of school supplies and materials is a cause of burnout and frustration among special education teachers. In the study, the lacking resources often involved inadequate number of books for every student, lack of a functional computer in the classroom, teachers' manuals, and other basic consumable

materials. Meanwhile, the results of the present study show a similar case. P6 highlighted that there has been a consistent shortage of teaching materials in their school. The problem elicits stress to teachers as this may affect the efficiency of their execution of learning activities in the classroom. Meanwhile, P7 mentioned that the classrooms need improvement, indicating that the learning environment may not be conducive for teachers and students. The study of Ihekoronye (2020) emphasized the importance of a comfortable classroom set up in order to produce a positive learning atmosphere to enforce a better learning process. Furthermore, P9 noted that the lack of training and resources

in connection with online learning likewise resulted to several difficulties in the learning process.

3.1.2. Lack of Appreciation—An environment where efforts are appreciated and commended inspires workers to give their best. Employees place a higher value on receiving respect, engaging in fulfilling work, having a sense of fulfillment, and having open lines of communication with one another (Sia, 2012). Acknowledgment demonstrates workforce con-

3.1.3. Heavy workload—Teaching is a demanding profession and educators are often required to accomplish multiple tasks at a short period of time. However, this harsh work conditions, coupled with an unsupportive environment, may lead to burnout. Werang (2018) suggested that heavy workload could contribute to the detriment of teachers' emotional health. It was revealed that workload, personal traits, and school environment all had a substantial favorable impact on primary school teachers' emotional weariness. Often, insurmountable workload is one of the reasons why teachers feel stressed. These results may be valuable to school administrators and the Department of Education in eradicating teachers' emotional burnout through the development of various initiatives that, on the one hand, enhance the workload structure and school environment and, on the other, develop the diligent nature of teachers.

3.1.4. High pressure expectations—Setting expectations in a workplace could help in realizing goals and objectives. However, too much pressure and emphasis on these expectations may lead to negative feelings. According to Troman and Peter Woods (2000), the recruitment and retention of teachers could be pointed to the high pressure demands of the profession which root from constant changed organization and nature of their work. P4 emphasized that there is a mismatch in the expected academic

confidence, and motivate workers to produce more. Thus, a lack of appreciation in the workplace may elicit a counterproductive result. P2 highlighted that the absence of a supportive work environment caused further stress among educators. This may encompass a lack of a sense of community in the school setting and unhinged dynamics between teachers and administrators, among many others.

outcomes and teaching support. Often times, teachers are anticipated to produce high results with little to no resources available, which could be difficult to achieve. Meanwhile, P5 highlighted that the day-to-day tasks of teachers are highly demanding to the point where it often leaves little personal time. More so, there is an expected need to constantly communicate with parents, which is an addition to stress and demands of the job, according to P7. Furthermore, P10 highlighted that there is also a demand to produce high-achieving students, in terms of academic, to the point where their holistic development becomes severely overlooked. The study revealed that extreme standards are one of the main causes of burnout for teachers. Stress spirals out of control when teachers are under constant pressure to reach high standards, balance administrative responsibilities, and fulfill the requirements of a varied student body. These elevated anticipations frequently result in extended work hours, amplified psychological stress, and an enduring sense of never doing enough. Teachers may have to give up personal time, find it difficult to strike a balance between work and life, and become emotionally worn out trying to meet expectations that don't seem realistic. Chronic stress can eventually result in burnout, which has an adverse effect on a teacher's health as well as their ability to teach effectively and the standard of instruction that pupils get.

Fig. 3. DepEd Teachers’ Experiences with Occupational Stress and Burnout

3.2. Coping Mechanisms—

3.2.1. *Planning of Tasks*—One of the emerging themes extracted from the analysis is the planning of tasks. When tasks are not planned, they might accumulate and become overwhelming, leading to stress and burnout. Planning helps break larger tasks into smaller, more manageable steps, preventing a sense of being buried under an unmanageable workload. As a coping strategy, planning has been instrumental for public school teachers in withstanding the challenges of stress and burnout. P1 emphasized the benefit of crafting a personalized comprehensive plan in work. P6 reinforced setting appropriate activities to keep with the demands. On the other hand, P9 shared the role of keeping up with the workplace guidelines and policies. These sentiments by the public-

school teachers are emanated in the findings of the study of Kebbi and Al-Hroub (2018) which revealed that one of the most common coping strategy teachers used is organizing time and setting priorities. Teachers who plan their deliverables in a pace beneficial for them, would count as a strategy to eliminate stress and burnout. As a result, stressors cannot be eliminated from teaching, thus teachers must develop strategies and techniques to handle them while maintaining teaching and personal efficacy (Waltz, 2016). Teachers must learn to see the bright side of things in order to effectively deal with the causes of stress in the classroom and manage their time. Consequently, an optimistic attitude toward achieving new changes in school reforms through collective proactive measures lowered stress (Tikkanen et al., 2020).

3.2.2. *Collaboration*—

The second coping strategy that was employed by public school teachers was collaboration. Collaborative environments foster a strong support system among teachers. Sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions allows teachers to seek advice, guidance, and emotional support from colleagues, reducing stress levels. P2 emphasized that interacting with coworkers has helped to reduce workplace stress. Similarly, P7 pointed out that involvement in discussions highlighting best practices and stress management approaches aided them in their stress understanding. Meanwhile, P6 noted that collaborating with other teachers in the field would offer positive effects, particularly in terms of increasing students' learning experiences. These findings are consistent with the findings of Li et al. (2022) which found that teachers frequently rely on social support networks, such as colleagues, mentors, and support groups, as an important coping technique. Peer engagement and sharing experiences protect against burnout by providing emotional support and a sense of

belonging. Accordingly, an effective support system was discovered to be a potential source of coping (Cezar-Vaz et al., 2015; Khan et al., 2014). On the contrary, another set of study posited that another stressor to the teachers is their relationship with their colleagues. Sabherwal et al. (2015) revealed that poor relationships with the administration and colleagues cause occupational stress among teachers. This was confirmed in the research of Anbazhagan and Selvan (2022) involving 220 teachers in India validated this finding, noting that the dynamics of teacher interactions at school contributed to some of the stress that teachers face. Furthermore, Akpınar (2008) noted that teachers' stress is caused by colleagues' competition and ambition, widespread gossiping, shirking work, having disagreements, and not receiving assistance. Teachers' stress levels can also be increased by being exposed to a lot of change and having difficult or challenging interactions with colleagues and administration (Kyriacou, 2001).

3.2.3. Approaches in handling learners— The third extracted theme for teachers' coping mechanisms against stress and burnout was the various techniques in dealing with students. Teachers can assist alleviate the impact of stress and burnout on learners by employing a variety of strategies and being proactive in supporting students' well-being, resulting in a healthier and more conducive learning environment. Respondents, on the other hand, believed that teachers should embrace optimism while dealing with students. P8 highlighted that it in working with diverse learners, teachers must be patient and empathetic. This was reinforced by P10 who advocated that while pressure is in place, learners must always be considered upfront. On the other hand, P3 recognized that various approaches must be taken into account considering the learners' unique characteristics. External

variables such as positive student responses inspired the majority of the teachers in this study. A better grasp of the teaching and learning process has sometimes assisted teachers in taking appropriate measures, particularly when dealing with diverse problems. This was accomplished by chatting to students, building relationship with them by listening to their difficulties, and considering their opinions (Amzat et al., 2021). Teachers stated that they were realistic and opposed pressuring children to learn. They recognized that children had diverse capacities and cognitive processes to execute as part of the teaching and learning process. However, according to Amorio and Torion (2021), some of the stress and burnout experienced by teachers are caused by irresponsible behavior of students, such as using profane language. When they heard their students' unwholesome language,

Fig. 4. DepEd Teachers’ Coping Mechanisms for Occupational Stress and Burnout
 the responses became extremely sensitive. This type of student behavior may significantly affect to poor performance for teachers at work. Furthermore, in order to suffer less occupational stress, teachers must believe in themselves. As a result, if the teacher wishes to be stress-free,

they should learn to be emotionally prepared, particularly while dealing with students. These findings suggest that teachers adjust to surroundings, resulting in greater pleasure and reduced stress.

3.3. Educational Management Insights—

3.3.1. Overwhelming Workload—The first educational management insight that appeared in this study was the overwhelming workload of teachers. Performing multiple roles and engaging with unnecessary workloads has become the reason of teachers’ stress and burnout. P1 said that lesson planning, grading, and administrative chores took up a significant amount of time

at work. P3 presented herself as a counselor and disciplinarian, among other things. P9 backed up the notion of role multiplicity. Teachers admitted to failing to handle stressful conditions at work and to remain calm in challenging scenarios. This self-reported rating could be linked to teachers’ heavy workload. According to research, each teacher works 12.17 hours a day,

has five classes, and teaches 141 pupils on average. These factors contribute to extremely high stress and emotional weariness, moderate depersonalization, and moderate personal achievement (Cammayo et al., 2022). These findings are also supported by Jimenez (2021) study which found that teachers have a variety of responsibilities, including, but not limited to, motivating students, planning lessons, imparting knowledge and skills, maintaining classroom discipline, and keeping parents informed of their students' progress. The findings served as additional evidence that, in addition to their daily six hours or more of instruction, public school teachers are overloaded with work-related responsibilities like reports, lesson plans, school designations, and other related tasks. This working environment causes teachers' performance to fall short of the aim, which is above proficiency level. Given this workload, the numerous duties and activities that teachers perform are taking priority over real teaching tasks (David et al., 2020 as quoted in Jimenez, 2021). On the other hand, a sole subtheme re-

duction of administrative tasks was generated as a complement for the overwhelming workload. Both P9 and P3 are in unison that administrative tasks must be reduced and that the department must hire non-teaching staff to cover such works. Similarly, they believe that their job requires too much administrative paperwork and that their personal goals are occasionally compromised owing to time constraints. Teachers are likely to experience burnout as a result of their profession due to the nature of their work and professional responsibilities. It is associated to a sense of emptiness caused by job-related demands, stressors, and work overload (Maslach Leiter, 2016). The Department of Education has recently taken steps to reduce teachers' administrative responsibilities by hiring extra non-teaching personnel. Sara Z. Duterte, Vice President and Secretary of Education, stated that teachers will soon be liberated of administrative obligations that hinder them from focusing on or improving students' learning by recruiting extra non-teaching staff (Doctolero, 2023).

3.3.2. Continued Professional Development. —The second theme generated for the insights was continued professional development (CPD). Professional development lays a significant role in preventing teacher burnout and stress by offering ongoing opportunities for growth, learning, and support. By investing in CPD, schools and educational institutions can significantly contribute to preventing burnout and stress among their teaching personnel. P4 deduced that CPD are essential in the pedagogical skills of the teachers. Meanwhile, the respondent added that without these, teachers may end dissatisfied of their jobs. These findings are in alignment with the study of Guskey and Yoon (2019) which concluded that teachers who actively participate in CPD activities report higher job satisfaction, which acts as a buffer

against burnout and stress. In addition, a study by Prodigy (2019) asserted that professional development can help new and experienced teachers develop the skills they need to feel confident in the classroom. Teachers who have access to continuous learning opportunities and professional development tools are better prepared to become successful teachers, especially whether their pupils have learning needs or perform below or above grade level. As a result, teachers will be able to handle stress and burnout more professionally. Furthermore, Kebbi and Al-Hroub (2018) proposed that early in their careers, adequate and specific stress management training for teachers might be devised, taking into account the educational level in which they will teach as well as the corresponding job expectations. It should be planned and imple-

mented to provide educators with training on how to maintain a balance between work demands and duties and personal and social-life time, how to set realistic goals and achieve them, how to communicate and maintain supportive relationships in the workplace, and how to de-

3.3.3. Strengthened Social Support—The third educational management insight theme is social support. Social support improves quality of life and acts as a buffer against negative life occurrences in any job. This shows that teachers witnessed their superiors and coworkers giving them with the necessary social support in the workplace. P8 advocated for a strong support system from parents and administrators. Meanwhile, P10 called for greater support through home-school partnerships. These findings indicate that teachers believe that having good and strong relationships with parents, students, and colleagues, as well as being able to interact socially with them, has assisted them in reducing work stress and burnout. According to Hurst, Wallace, and Nixon (2013), the best teachers are those who are highly inspired and determined to improve their students' learning experiences as well as the quality of their interactions with school officials and parents. If they believe that communicating with others would benefit them,

velop stress-coping strategies. In closing, CPD helps teachers feel more competent and less overwhelmed by offering tools and resources to manage workload and negotiate challenges, thereby reducing stress levels.

they will make an attempt to communicate with others and devote their time. They will also take part in educational activities that they believe would help them become better teachers. According to Sourjah (2021), when teachers have instrumental support in their lives, they feel less alone and have a stable support network to fall back on. This enables teachers to tackle difficulties with gratitude and positivity. According to Jolly et al. (2020), colleagues who provide empathy, guidance, and a listening ear can assist teachers in navigating difficult situations, minimizing feelings of emotional tiredness, depersonalization, and decreased personal accomplishment—all of which are major components of burnout (Schaufeli Maslach, 2017). Social support within the educational system is critical in reducing stress and minimizing teacher burnout. Building strong support networks, cultivating positive connections, and fostering a culture of mutual support and understanding are critical predictors for promoting a healthy work environment and boosting teachers' well-being.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this part of the paper, the study's summary is presented, using the findings, I drew the implications as well as future directions. The study aimed to explore the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of teachers in dealing with burnout and stress in the workplace. Insights have likewise been drawn from the results. The participants were teachers from the Schools Division of Davao City, Region XI. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, I used the qualitative phenomenological research design. Thematic analysis was also utilized to analyze the themes of the study. Following the recommendations provided by Cresswell (2006), open-ended interview questions were used to gain a genuine insight of participants' experiences. Additionally, by using this interviewing technique, I allowed my participants to freely and honestly share how they understood the issue under investigation—public elementary school teachers'

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights from DepEd Teachers' Experiences with Occupational Stress and Burnout

experiences in dealing with burnout and stress in the workplace.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis, the following themes were discovered. The challenges experienced by teachers involving stress and burnout in the workplace involved the lack of resources, lack of appreciation, heavy workload and high-pressure expectations. The findings revealed that the lack of learning resources such as school materials, textbooks, facilities, and a conducive classroom environment caused stress and burnout to educators. Lacking resources have significantly impacted teachers' motivations to deliver their lessons, thus affecting educational quality. Meanwhile, the participants also reported that the lack of appreciation for the work that they do also have some negative implications, resulting to stress and burnout. An unhealthy work environment with no support from colleagues and administrators was difficult to navigate, according to the study participants. Teachers also reiterated that they felt like their occupation is not being valued by society enough, as reflected in its meager pay and unfavorable work conditions. Another theme that transpired was the heavy workload. The demands of the job took up so much of teachers' time and energy, often compromising their personal life and moments for their families. Finally, high-pressure expectations were revealed by the study participants to be the last source of their burnout. The expected outcomes of their work are so high yet the resources available are scarce. This often leads to teachers' stress and burnout in the workplace. Meanwhile, the results of the study showed that educators use the following coping mechanisms to deal with occupational stress and burnout: planning of tasks, collaboration, and approaches in handling learners. The amount of workload that teachers need to accomplish calls for an effective and efficient task planning. This helps teachers to manage their time better for their career and personal life. More so, planning ahead for important responsibilities at work helped them lessen the level of stress and anxiety that they experience in their jobs. Furthermore, collaborating with their colleagues at school also helps in minimizing the negative psychological impact of the demands of the job. This involves participating in seminars or discussions to approach problems at work. Additionally, learners' unruly behavior is easily one of the contributing sources of stress for educators. Keeping up with classroom management approaches to deal with difficult learner behavior is likewise used by teachers. The educational management insights drawn from the study findings were overwhelming workload, continued professional development, and strengthened social support. It can be surmised from the results of the study that teaching is indeed a high-pressure career and teachers are often subjected to poor working conditions coupled with an overwhelming amount of work – a reality that must be acknowledged and given solution. In their day-to-day work, teachers also often face different forms of problems. Continued professional development, particularly in the digital era, must be encouraged, in order to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to deal with the evolving times. Moreover, school communities must likewise establish a strong social support among teachers and administrators in order to handle problems at work. This would also help in creating an atmosphere that is positive and encouraging.

4.2. Implications—The results of the analysis revealed the following significant findings: Teachers face different kinds of problems in their occupation which often lead to stress and

burnout. The said challenges encompass the lack of resources, such as textbook materials, good facilities, and a conducive classroom environment. All of these affect educational quality and students' learning outcomes. Better support for teachers regarding this aspect should be given priority by the Department of Education, as well as school administrators. Moreover, the findings revealed that teacher participants felt like they were undervalued. Teachers' salaries do not justify the amount of work demands, as teachers are constantly faced with heavy workload, thus compromising their personal time for themselves and their families. This could lead to negative feelings about their chosen profession, which could affect the quality of their performance at work. This also influences students' learning outcomes. Finally, the high-pressure expectations of their job coming from administrators, colleagues, students, parents, and other

stakeholders could be detrimental to their well-being. The participants highlighted that the expectation to produce high quality results with very little support and resources caused a negative toll on their mental health. The implications suggest that in order to properly resolve the challenges associated to teachers' occupational stress and burnout, a strong support system in terms of resources and community must be improved. Teachers need to feel that they are being supported and that they can rely on others in times of difficulties. Maintaining a systematic workflow and efficient stream of instructions are also keys to reducing stress and burnout because teachers can plan ahead about their tasks. Collaboration must also be practiced within the school community. All these can help in maintaining a kind of environment that is appreciative, cooperative, and healthy for the overall well-being of educators.

4.3. *Future Directions*—The following future directions were surmised based on the findings of the study: The Department of Education could come up with reforms to relieve teachers of their heavy workload, particularly of tasks that do not directly involve the teaching and learning process, such as clerical or administrative tasks. The lack of learning materials in schools should also be addressed in order to better equip students and teachers with the necessary resources to engage in the process of teaching and learning. More so, policymakers should give teachers the proper compensation that is justifiable to the demands and amount of work that they do. This can also help elevate the status of the profession to attract skilled

teachers in the future. Moreover, this can also help in reducing, if not eliminating, the inclination of quality teachers to seek overseas work. Teachers may also engage themselves in individual efforts to cope with the circumstances of their occupation, such as deepening their relationships with supportive colleagues or the community. Additionally, they may craft plans and strategies to achieve their work goals efficiently such as planning ahead for important work responsibilities. Future researchers can also participate on the same research with a different set of participants and demographics. Other means that have been used in this research may likewise be explored or utilized for better outcomes.

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